

TECHNOLOGIES OF APPLICATION OF RHYTHMIC EXERCISES IN PRIMARY DISABLED CHILDREN

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Annotation: *To study the speech of children who stutter in the article. Methods of developing independent speech in speechless children, conversations with speech therapists, educators and parents, testing of independent speech in children, improvement of children's independent speech development are described.*

Keywords: *mental development, specific gender and age characteristics, alalia, aphasia, rhinolalia, neurotic stuttering, neurotic stuttering, cognitive, cognitive and affective aspects, genetic, social and personal factors, diagnostic and correction processes, phonetic, lexical and grammatical tools.*

Today, one of the most important issues is to improve the quality of education, to raise it to the level of world standards, to apply innovations in science. Educating the younger generation, developing their knowledge, skills and abilities in the basics of science is one of the priorities of state policy.

In particular, in order to further improve the system of preschool education, to ensure equal access to quality preschool education for children, to develop the non-governmental sector of preschool education services, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev to create conditions for the comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of preschool children, to increase the coverage of children with quality preschool education, to provide equal opportunities for them development of public-private partnership in this area, ensuring healthy and balanced nutrition of children in preschool institutions, quality medical care, preschool education, which is today the highest link of the education system The issue of educating the younger generation in the system is cross-cutting. It is the psychological formation of the moral behavior in their upbringing that is becoming a topical issue today.

Preschool is such a meaningful and active period that it will have a significant impact on the child's future development. Therefore, the preschool period is very responsible in terms of impact. By the time he reaches preschool age, his mental development will have undergone significant changes. Because from the same period the child's independent activity expands considerably. Preschoolers have two powerful forces that they need to be able to work independently. Firstly, he has a somewhat subordinate movement apparatus, and secondly, he has a speech that allows him to interact more freely with the adults around him and his peers.

That is why the behaviors, moral qualities, behaviors, interests and needs of children of this age are drastically different from those of children of the first age. This, in turn, requires a different approach to early childhood education and preschool education. Preschoolers make a significant difference in their relationship with the environment. On the one hand, the child becomes more free from the constant help of adults, and on the other hand, his relationship with adults becomes more complex and multifaceted. Therefore, the formation of speech in children with stuttering is carried out mainly in kindergarten by educators, speech therapists and speech pathologists through various activities. In the classes, children gain new knowledge and skills, as well as general and verbal behavioral skills, and the ability to use speech independently without stuttering.

Stuttering children develop the ability to perform learning activities in accordance with a single oral instruction without verbal instructions and demonstrations or sample demonstrations, develop cognition, memory, thinking, curiosity, and management processes. Children learn to answer specific and general questions; speech therapist, practice short and wide responses at the request of the educator; at a normal tempo, understandable to others, loud enough, clear, meaningful. The lessons will strengthen the skills of using the grammatical forms of nouns, adjectives and other parts of the language.

An integral part of the training is the development of such qualities as concentration, comprehension, memory, active participation in the dialogue, and, if necessary, abstinence from impulsive statements. Develops the ability to start and finish work at the same time without going ahead and behind their peers, normal pace of activity, mobility, coordination, habit of working in sequence, finishing work, distribution of attention between the two types of activities, (paper) rational consumption, manuals, proper use of weapons are formed. Particular attention is paid to the development of positive personal qualities and general and verbal behavioral skills, as well as the development of skills of independent speech. It is also necessary to develop the ability to play not only in a team, but also individually,

to subdue or limit their desires in accordance with the rules of the game, to cultivate the qualities of will: self-control, self-discipline. great emphasis is placed on responsibility for their actions, concentration, being active in the game, and at the same time being able to control their emotions and desires if necessary.

Speech correction during the game. To develop interest and love for work in children with disabilities, like children in public kindergartens, to teach them to perform work tasks actively and thoroughly, to cultivate the desire to achieve results, the willingness to participate in joint work with all children should. The educator develops in preschool children the skills of easy work, respect for the work of adults and peers, and at the same time strengthens the knowledge of the tools of labor. It is very important for preschoolers to pay attention to adult speech during work, to cultivate patience, concentration, and purposefulness. They should be able to listen to the task until the end and then begin to complete it. In addition to the general tasks of working with stuttering children, regime moments should also be used to correct speech activity, such as their general and verbal behaviors.

On the agenda are a number of convenient opportunities to organize a direct speech without stuttering, about which you can organize a conversation with children. It is important to organize children during communication. It is advisable to hold them correctly so that children love each other (circle, semicircle). In order for children to participate in the conversation, all the moments must be clearly organized: washing, dressing, undressing, duty, excursions, observation, etc. Children should be taught to perform all actions without excessive noise, to listen to adult speech and peer answers, to respond when asked a question, and to not interrupt their peers.

Special attention is paid to adult speech. They should be quiet in their speech, and the questions should be clearly formulated by following the pauses between the child's question and answer. You need to give them time to think about the answer, speak at a normal pace, not slow down their personal speech, and not ask children to slow down their speech. Basic requirements for speech therapy classes for children with stuttering:

1) Speech therapy classes reflect the main tasks of pedagogical and correctional influence on the speech and personality of a stuttering child.

2) Speech therapy classes in a certain order, continuous, step-by-step, taking into account the basic didactic principles, depending on the individual characteristics of each child; based on the awareness and activity of children; manuals, visual aids, technical aids are used in the lessons; the sessions help to reinforce the correct speech and behavioral skills being nurtured.

3) Speech therapy classes meet the requirements of the programs of education and training of preschool and school-age children.

4) The lessons take into account the need to practice the correct speech and behavior of children who stutter in different situations, for example: in the speech therapy room and beyond, in different life situations, with the participation of acquaintances and strangers, etc. For this purpose, various forms of speech therapy classes: many forms of work on speech development, didactic, action, role-playing and creative games, trips, mornings, preparation for and participation in concerts, speaking in front of a microphone and others.

5) Classes are organized in such a way that the child should be able to speak without stuttering and with the disorders that accompany it.

6) Exercises strengthen the child's good mood, endurance, self-confidence.

7) Classes of correct speech are regularly attended by speech therapists, effective children's speech, tape recordings and plates with speeches of masters of artistic expression, ceremonial speeches of those who have successfully completed a speech therapy course, etc. .

8) Classes are based on the correct attitude of others towards the stuttering child and his proper upbringing.

In short, in children, this defect is mainly due to imbalances in the processes of excitation and braking. According to the speech therapist's advice, you should consult a specialist as soon as you notice that your child has a speech delay or mispronounces or stutters. The earlier you apply, the more effectively speech defects will be eliminated.

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